

The Closure Signature: a New Approach to Model Soft Robotic Hands

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Abstract—Underactuated and compliant hands are gaining the attention of the robotic grasping community mainly due to their simple kinematics, intrinsic compliance and versatility for grasping objects in non structured environments. However, predicting, modelling, and controlling their behaviour, can present also some challenges. This abstract summarizes research efforts carried out to introduce a completely new way of representing robotic hands, that cuts ties with traditional grasp models and focuses more on the hand capabilities, rather than its kinematic structure.

I. INTRODUCTION

Underactuated and compliant hands, frequently referred to as soft hands, have been recently proposed to overcome common issues of multi-fingered robotic hands [1], [2]. Although several prototypes have been developed, there is still a lack of systematic ways to model and control these devices to get grasps exploiting their intrinsic features. Classical tools can hardly be applied when contact surfaces are deformable and hand kinematics is not uniquely defined due to underactuation. This abstract summarizes a recently published work where we propose a method to model underactuated compliant hands [3] (PDF) (Video). The model captures how the hand closes analysing the motion of suitable reference points defined on the hand. In particular, we present a procedure to compute the preferred grasping direction of a given hand, namely the *closure signature* (CS), and then we use this information to plan power grasps. The feasibility of the proposed method has been validated by performing experiments with a soft hand fixed to a robotic arm. The use of the closure signature proved to increase the performance of the grasp planner. The proposed method can easily be extended to other underactuated compliant hands.

II. CLOSURE SIGNATURE COMPUTATION

The procedure to obtain the CS has to be performed only once for each hand closure motion. The resulting CS is specific for a given hand and a given closing motion and is a way to represent how the hand closes in free space, *i.e.*, without considering interaction with a grasped object. If the hand has only one degree of actuation (DoA), like the Pisa/IIT SoftHand [1], there is only one possible closing

motion, so there is only one possible CS. In case of multiple DoAs, the CS could be used to represent achievable hand closing motions. For the RBO Hand 2 [2], that has 4 degrees of actuation, we can, for example, choose to model a closure that is similar to the first human hand postural synergy [4]. In general, the idea is that for a given control input, the fingers close with a certain trajectory and the CS models this movement.

To compute the CS, a set of reference points must be defined on the robotic hand and tracked during the closure motion that we want to model. Measuring the overall motion of the reference points, we can evaluate an equivalent linear transformation and from the analysis of this transformation we can define the hand closure signature, that is the *direction* (indicated by the unit vector \mathbf{v}_{CS}) along which the hand produces the highest deformation while closing. In addition to the direction, we also need to compute an application point for the versor \mathbf{v}_{CS} , namely \mathbf{o}_h , as the centroid of all the trajectories of the reference points.

More details on the computations can be found in [3], where we also analysed the closure signature of two grippers and of the Pisa/IIT SoftHand.

The Pisa/IIT SoftHand is an anthropomorphic underactuated soft robotic hand with 19 joints controlled by a single actuator. The actuated movement of the hand resembles the first human hand synergy, as defined in [4]. We chose the hand fingertips as reference points and we tracked them with the Gazebo simulator [5] from an initial position (completely open hand) to a final position (completely closed hand), see Fig. 1a. The black dots in Fig. 1b represent the reference points trajectories, while the blue vector is the CS of the Pisa/IIT SoftHand. In [3], studies on the sensitivity of the computed CS to the variations of the parameters can be found.

III. PLANNING GRASPS WITH THE CLOSURE SIGNATURE

In this section, we propose a procedure for planning top-grasps exploiting the closure signature of a soft hand, computed as in Sec. II. The main idea of the grasp planner is to align the closure signature of the hand to a potentially good direction to grasp a given object. Consider, for instance, a simple cuboid object, that could be the result of the approximation of an object with a bounding box procedure. A potentially good grasping direction for the object can be defined as in Fig. 1c, considering the direction connecting the two middle points of the longest faces of the bounding box that are also perpendicular to the table. In general, more

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Fig. 1: (a) Pisa/IIT SoftHand fully open and fully closed in the Gazebo simulation. (b) Trajectories of the contact points (black) from the initial position (orange), to the final position (light blue), and closure signature (blue vector applied in O_h). (c) Top-grasp planning, main definitions. The preferred grasp direction on the object bounding box, BBD , is parallel to the shortest edge of the object bounding box, and passing through its centre. The transformation T_{CS} brings CS aligned to BBD . (d) The experimental setup. A UR5 robotic arm was used to move the Pisa/IIT SoftHand. An ATI Gamma sensor is added between the end effector of the robot and the hand to measure the interaction of the hand with the environment.

complex procedures could be employed to determine the grasping direction of the object.

Using an experimental setup composed of a robotic arm and a soft hand, the Pisa/IIT SoftHand (see Fig. 1d), we verified that by aligning the hand CS direction (CS in Fig. 1c) with a suitable grasping direction on the object (BBD in Fig. 1c), hand’s grasping performance improve in terms of grasp quality, robustness to uncertainties, and number of successful grasps.

To show the the effectiveness of the grasp planning algorithm based on the closure signature (CS -alignment), we performed two experiments comparing it with the method proposed in [6], where simulated grasps with the SoftHand are obtained by aligning the hand to the bounding boxes in which the object is decomposed. We used a simplified version of this alignment algorithm, where we considered the bounding box of the entire object. We refer to this method as “Straight alignment” (S -alignment). The following paragraphs summarize the main results that we obtained.

a) The CS -alignment is robust to uncertainty on object pose: We tested the S -alignment and the CS -alignment with three prototypical objects: one box-shaped, one cylindrical, and one approximately spherical (apple). Each object was placed on the table and grasped by the robot, either by aligning BBD (the object’s x direction, parallel to the shortest edge of the bounding box) straightly to the robot hand’s x -axis (S -alignment), or to the computed closure signature (CS -alignment). To assess the robustness of the approach, uncertainty was added to the object pose by a transformation defined by a random rotation $r_r \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_r^2)$ around the z -axis and translation $t = [t_x, t_y, 0]^T$, $t_x, t_y \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_t^2)$. We used three different levels of uncertainty on the object pose and, for each type of grasp, 20 trials were executed. Both strategies worked well in case of no uncertainty on the object pose, and this mainly comes from the fact that the compliance of the hand compensates for uncertainties on the object dynamic properties. When uncertainties on the object

pose were added, the CS -alignment was found to be more robust than the other one, especially for the cylinder and for the box [3].

b) The CS -alignment increases the percentage of successful grasps: The alignment strategy for top-grasps was tested on other 19 different objects, chosen also within the YCB Object Set [7], and including boxes, cylinders and spheres of different sizes, weights, and materials, and objects with less regular shapes.

In total, we performed 190 grasps per strategy. The CS -alignment and the S -alignment had a success rate of $\sim 85\%$ (161/190) and of $\sim 68\%$ (130/190), respectively.

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